

DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE METHODS FOR DESIGNING INDUSTRIAL BUILDINGS

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Аннотация: Дизайн эчимлари вариантларини баҳолаш ва улардан энг яхшисини танлашда назарий қийинчиликлар билан боғлиқ бир қатор сабаблар ўрганилган. Бугунги кундаги лойиҳаланаётган саноат биноларининг қанча қисми вирианти лойиҳаланмоқда, вариантли лойиҳаланмаслигига сабаб нима ва вариантли лойиҳаларни амалга ошириш учун таклифлар.

Аннотация: Исследован ряд причин, связанных с теоретическими трудностями оценки вариантов проектных решений и выбора оптимального из них. Сколько частей промышленных зданий сегодня проектируются вариантно, в чем причина непроектирования варианта и предложения по вариантные проекты.

Annotation: A number of reasons related to the theoretical difficulties in evaluating design solution options and choosing the best of them have been explored. How many parts of industrial buildings are being designed today are variantly designed, what is the reason for not designing the option and proposals for variant projects.

Keyword: operational efficiency, design organizations, design methods, Optimal solutions, Google SketchUp, KZ-Kottedj, Arxikad, Revit, Planix Home 3D Architect, Ashampoo Home Designer, Industrial buildings, physical and technical foundations.

The purpose of the study: The most sensible design solution based on research is that it is a key resource to increase construction efficiency, reduce electricity, materials and labor costs. Experiments show that an alternative design can reduce construction costs by \$ 3-5, and the additional cost associated with developing options is \$ 10-15 per dollar.

As a result of research on the selection of optimal floors of the building, tex.f. Prof. Shatnev B.N. that is, by choosing the right number of floors for a building, a reduction in the area of exterior surfaces can be achieved, resulting in a reduction in heating costs from \$ 40 to \$ 30. Mixaylov G.I. emphasizes that the selection of reasonable parameters of an industrial

building is to increase construction efficiency and, most importantly, operational efficiency. To prove this, he cites the following figures: "By choosing the rational parameters of single-storey industrial buildings without additional costs, a significant reduction in the number of required structural elements can be achieved: the cost of columns and foundations, wall panels and windows up to \$ 30, construction materials consumption - 20 dollars, heating costs - more than halved. The placement of production in multi-storey buildings is carried out on a limited scale, taking into account the provision of high-level architectural solutions and to ensure the smallest area of the surrounding structures.

The analysis showed that today, on average, 8 out of 10 design organizations do not carry out variant design work in practice, 2 in which alternative research is carried out only on individual decisions, and only 2 organizations have the necessary funds for this.

The main reason for this situation, as mentioned above, is the increase in labor costs and design time in the search for rational solutions using traditional methods, and on the one hand the lack of methods that allow to overcome these negative consequences. use of computer technology.

There are also a number of reasons for the theoretical difficulties in evaluating design solution options in the early stages of development and choosing the best of them. The widespread introduction of modern computer programs in the design organizations of the Republic, research on improving the types of industrial buildings, as well as intensive theoretical developments related to decision-making in creative tasks have laid the foundation for the development of alternative design methods for industrial facilities.

It is necessary for the Institute to work purposefully to create the most rational types of production buildings for different purposes, to combine their parameters, to create a method of block design of standard designs of mass construction facilities. Research and training institutes have made significant strides in improving space planning solutions for industrial buildings. The following Russian scientists made a significant contribution to the development of this research: Aleshchenko N.V., Vlokhin V.V., Bovt I.I., Boris G.G., Whatman Ya.P., Vikhrev I.D., Gohar-Harmandaryan Y. .G., Demidov S.V., Dubson A.A., Istomin E.G., Kim H.H., Klyuchevich V.C., Myslin V.D., Nikolaev I.S., Khromets Yu.N. ., Khrustalev A.A., Shatnev B.N., Shubin L.F. et al.

The development of alternative design methods has encouraged the use of the latest advances in scientific fields to help improve the design

process. First, these are systems analysis methods that allow you to find the best options for design solutions taking into account a large number of factors, decision-making methods that allow you to evaluate them objectively. mathematical modeling methods and use of modern computer programs.

The study of options can be done without the use of modern computer technology, but this, as mentioned above, leads to a significant increase in labor costs and design time. Only the use of computers, which provide a practical opportunity to perform labor-intensive computational operations in the multidimensional search for optimal solutions, makes the study of the option really effective. At the same time, an important result is to reduce or stabilize the number of designers by reducing design time and increasing the volume of design work.

The main goal in automating the process of designing public-purpose facilities - residential, public and industrial buildings - is to obtain the most reasonable design solutions. This is because public-purpose facilities account for the bulk of capital investment in construction, and the inefficiency of their decisions can lead to significant material losses. In other cases, the main goal may be to increase labor productivity by reducing design time or the number of designers working. An example of this is the development of design solutions for complexes or structures that depend on the subsequent development of material production (computers, vehicles, power plants, etc.).

Results:

An expert who decides to design industrial buildings in a modern way faces the problem of pre-designing and planning it. There are special applications such as building and structure design programs to solve such problems. They ensure the accuracy of the calculations, allowing to provide a final view of the building in real time.

Using their capabilities, you can create a three-dimensional model of the house, taking into account the selected materials for construction, the desired color scheme and the connection to the necessary conditions of the surrounding landscape. Дастирий таъминотлар

- 1 Google SketchUp
- 2 KZ-Kottedj
- 3 Archaic
- 4 Revit
- 5 Planix Home 3D Architect

- 6 Ashampoo Home Designer
- 7 HouseCreator + Carcass
- 8 Arkhitekturnoe proektirovanie zdaniy i sooruzheniy
- 8.1 Constructive chast
- 8.2 Expenditures on constructions and materials

Address of the source:

<https://proekt-sam.ru/proektprogramms/programmy-dlya-proektirovaniya-zdaniy-i-sooruzheniy.html>

Working in these programs is simple, but requires basic skills. Like all construction programs, these have their pros and cons.

Pros:It can also be used by new users who know only the basics of working in software for designing buildings and structures.

It can be used to create projects in different groups, from individual users to design workshops.

To make changes to the model, simply set the desired inclination angle or draw a special section profile.

The number of moves from building a model to turning it into a drawing is minimal.

A lot of information is used to provide visual communication with the user: its characteristics are given in the selection of the object; to build the elements correctly, you can focus on the time lines that appear.

Conclusions and suggestions

We can design not only simple structures, but also buildings with complex shapes, place walls and beams at any angle, with any openings. Thanks to the automated system of document preparation, there is no problem in creating drawings.

The positions of the holes are easily controlled by fixing the height of the upper face.

In the program, you can customize pencil and color sets to create drawings at home. This is especially useful when preparing a set of documents.

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